

RADiation harvesting of bioactive peptides from egg **prO**teins and their integration in ad**V**anced functional products

INNOVATION ACTION OF HORIZON EUROPE EURATOM RESEARCH AND TRAINING
PROGRAMME GA N° 101061694

DELIVERABLE REPORT

PROJECT WEBSITE SETTING UP

DELIVERABLE: D5.1

Document identifier:	RADOV-Del-D5.1
Due date of deliverable:	End of month 6 (February 2023)
Report release date:	20/07/2023
Work package:	WP5 [Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation]
Lead beneficiary:	HUD
Document status:	Final

ABSTRACT

The RADOV website has been in development since the start of the project and is now launched in its full form. It can be found at <http://www.radov.eu>. This report documents the structure, content, and scope, as well as plans for future additions and developments.

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Training programme under Grant Agreement No 101061694.

RADOV began in September 2022 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

	Name		Partner	Date
Authored by	Rob Edgecock		HUD	17/07/2023
Edited by	Rob Edgecock		HUD	17/07/2023
Reviewed by	Dagmara Chmielewska-Śmietanko		INCT	20/07/2023
Approved by	Steering Committee			28/07/2023

Change Log

Version	Date	Amended by	Changes
v.1.0		HUD	First draft
v.2.0		INCT	Final formatting

Version Management

Reviewed by	All Partners
Approved by	All Partners
Authorized by	Coordinator, Dagmara Chmielewska-Śmietanko

1. Introduction

The RADOV website (<http://www.radov.eu>) serves as one of the most crucial communication and dissemination tools for the project. The site aims to report on the project as a whole, provide updates on the results arising from the project, and act as an information portal for visitors wishing to engage with the project. As such, the website will host general overview information, as well as more detailed information on specific elements of the work programme. In an effort to both inform and engage different stakeholder groups, the site has made design, content and accessibility considerations for a variety of audiences. These considerations also allow for future updates and additions to the site, to optimise its content, structure and technical details. In addition, the site hosts links to the project's publication database, events and newsletters.

2. Website Design

The RADOV public website was designed by making considerations of both the needs of the project as well as key stakeholders. The design considered:

- RADOV needs: Which information is to be communicated.
- Stakeholder needs: May vary according to familiarity with the project.
- Visibility: How to ensure the site is visible to the maximum number of visitors.
- User-friendliness: How easy is the site to navigate .

2.1 RADOV Needs

The RADOV project required the development of a website to serve as its primary communication tool, targeting a variety of different stakeholders. The site was to host crucial information about the aims, logistics and persons involved in the project, as well as to advertise news, results and events within RADOV.

2.2 Stakeholder Needs

In an effort to ensure the most relevant and engaging information was made available to all visitors, several stakeholder groups were considered. These include RADOV project partners, the international research community, members of industry, policy makers and the general public.

2.3 Visibility

In an effort to ensure maximum visibility of the RADOV website, the site was registered using the "EU" domain at the following address: <http://www.radov.eu>, though the pages themselves are on a server at the University of Huddersfield. This aimed to increase the site's page ranking on search engines such as Google, aiming to ensure it is returned as a result in a large number of searches.

Each page on the website has its own URL, allowing visitors to share and bookmark pages of interest. Although this URL has a page number, rather than a name, the title of the page appears whenever this is copied.

2.4 User friendliness

The RADOV website aims to be user-friendly for visitors from various different stakeholder groups. Visitors should be able to navigate the site without prior knowledge of its content or structure to access the information they need. In addition, RADOV members visiting the site should also be able to quickly access pages relevant to their work across the duration of the project.

3. Future Plans

It is planned to update the RADOV website on a regular basis with news, events, results and additional text, images and links, as required. In addition, new pages will be added within the project's duration, when the need arises. We will also enhance the website through search engine optimisation and the potential inclusion of social media subscription buttons for RADOV social media accounts.